

ICRET MTÜ

International Center for Research, Education and Training

Rahvusvaheline teadus-, haridus- ja koolituskeskus MTÜ

Non-profit organisation/Mittetulundusühing

Registry code: 80550594

TRAINING PROGRAM

For medical doctors, physicians, nurses

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MED 01010- Main types of Stroke: causes and risk factors.

Course Description

The Main types of Stroke: causes and risk factors courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Blood circulation of the brain and spinal cord. Classification of disorders of cerebral circulation.
- Ischemic stroke (etiology, pathogenesis, clinical picture).
- Hemorrhagic stroke (etiology, pathogenesis, clinical picture).
- Spinal cord stroke (etiology, pathogenesis, clinical picture).
- Treatment of ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes (basic and differential therapy).
- Stroke and COVID.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of disease.
- Being familiar with type of disease.
- Learning about type of disease.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- 9 hours

MED 01011- Sepsis, definition, etiology, treatment, Causes and Risk Factors, Diagnosis, treatment (current approaches to management).

Course Description

The Sepsis, definition, etiology, treatment, Causes and Risk Factors, Diagnosis, treatment (current approaches to management): courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- The Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock (Sepsis-3).
- Surviving Sepsis Campaign: Guidelines on the Management of Critically Ill Adults with Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19).
- Septic shock, Practice Essentials, background, pathophysiology, treatment.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01012- Cardiogenic shock. Causes, pathophysiology, management.

Course Description

The Cardiogenic shock. Causes, pathophysiology, management: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- (American College of Cardiology Foundation (ACCF)/American Heart Association (AHA), European Society of Cardiology (ESC) guidelines).

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01013- Pulmonary embolism.

Course Description

Pulmonary embolism: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- (2019 ESC Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism developed in collaboration with the European Respiratory Society (ERS): The Task Force for the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism of the European Society of Cardiology) Causes .Management

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01014- Shock, definition, Classification, hypovolemic shock (hemorrhagic shock), DIC syndrome.

Course Description

Shock, definition, Classification, hypovolemic shock (hemorrhagic shock), DIC syndrome: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Evaluation of and initial approach to the adult patient with undifferentiated hypotension and shock
- Evaluation and management of suspected sepsis and septic shock in adults
- Clinical manifestations and diagnosis of cardiogenic shock in acute myocardial infarction
- Etiology, clinical manifestations, and diagnosis of volume depletion in adults
- Recognition and initial assessment of shock in adult trauma
- Clinical presentation, evaluation, and diagnosis of the non-pregnant adult with suspected acute pulmonary embolism.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01015- Causes of cardiac arrest. Severe arrhythmia.

Course Description

Causes of cardiac arrest. Severe arrhythmia: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Overview of sudden cardiac arrest and sudden cardiac death.
- Advanced cardiac life support (ACLS) in adults.
- Cardiac evaluation of the survivor of sudden cardiac arrest.
- Prognosis and outcomes following sudden cardiac arrest in adults.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01016- COPD exacerbation. Pathophysiology, treatment, CO2 removal devices, High flow cannula.

Course Description

COPD exacerbation. Pathophysiology, treatment, CO2 removal devices, High flow cannula: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Management of exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.
- Management of infection in exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.
- Evaluation for infection in exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: Definition, clinical manifestations, diagnosis, and staging.
- Noninvasive ventilation in adults with acute respiratory failure: Benefits and contraindications
- Moraxella catarrhalis infections.
- Arrhythmias in COPD.
- Invasive mechanical ventilation in acute respiratory failure complicating chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.
- Management of the patient with COPD and cardiovascular disease.
- Resistance of Streptococcus pneumoniae to the fluoroquinolones, doxycycline, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01017- High blood pressure in Emergency Room

Course Description

High blood pressure in Emergency Room: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Evaluation and treatment of hypertensive emergencies in adults.
- Drugs used for the treatment of hypertensive emergencies.
- Approach to hypertensive emergencies and urgencies in children.
- Overview of hypertension in adults.
- Management of severe asymptomatic hypertension (hypertensive urgencies) in adults.
- Emergency department approach to nontraumatic headache in children.
- Initial management of hypertensive emergencies and urgencies in children.
- Anesthesia for patients with hypertension.
- Hypertensive disorders in pregnancy: Approach to differential diagnosis.
- Management of hypertension in infants.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01018- Syncope and Vertigo

Course Description

Syncope and Vertigo: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Syncope in adults: Clinical manifestations and initial diagnostic valuation
- Approach to the patient with dizziness
- Syncope in adults: Epidemiology, pathogenesis, and etiologies
- Causes of syncope in children and adolescents
- Evaluation of dizziness and vertigo in children and adolescents
- Evaluation of the patient with vertigo
- Causes of dizziness and vertigo in children and adolescents
- Approach to the adult patient with syncope in the emergency department
- Nonepileptic paroxysmal disorders in children
- Clinical features and diagnosis of Takayasu arteritis

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01019- Vaginal bleeding in ER

Course Description

Vaginal bleeding in ER: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Abnormal uterine bleeding in adolescents: Evaluation and approach to diagnosis.
- Approach to the adult with vaginal bleeding in the emergency department.
- Approach to abnormal uterine bleeding in nonpregnant reproductive-age patients.
- Abnormal uterine bleeding in reproductive-age women: Terminology and PALM-COEIN etiology classification.
- Overview of the etiology and evaluation of vaginal bleeding in pregnant women.
- Abnormal uterine bleeding: Management in premenopausal patients.
- Differential diagnosis of genital tract bleeding in women.
- Abnormal uterine bleeding in adolescents: Management.
- Evaluation of vulvovaginal bleeding in children and adolescents.
- Evaluation and management of unscheduled bleeding in women using contraception.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01020- ABCDE and triage

Course Description

High blood pressure in Emergency Room: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Dermoscopic algorithms for skin cancer triage.
- Prehospital care of the adult trauma patient.
- Melanoma: Clinical features and diagnosis.
- Classification of trauma in children.
- Management of radiation injury.
- Chemical terrorism: Rapid recognition and initial medical management.
- Preparing an office practice for pediatric emergencies.
- Overview of the management of the severely burned patient.
- Disaster settings: Care of pregnant patients.
- Geriatric trauma: Initial evaluation and management.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

MED 01021- Abdominal and chest trauma

Course Description

High blood pressure in Emergency Room: courses provide the participants with an understanding of the character of disease. This course introduces the participants to the basic concepts of disease.

Course description in next details:

- Chest wall injuries after blunt trauma in children.
- Overview of blunt and penetrating thoracic vascular injury in adults.
- Emergency ultrasound in adults with abdominal and thoracic trauma.
- Initial evaluation and management of chest wall trauma in adults.
- Initial evaluation and management of penetrating thoracic trauma in adults.
- Initial evaluation and management of blunt thoracic trauma in adults.
- Approach to the initially stable child with blunt or penetrating injury.
- Thoracic trauma in children: Initial stabilization and evaluation.
- Overview of esophageal perforation due to blunt or penetrating trauma.
- Geriatric trauma: Initial evaluation and management.

Course Objectives

- Understanding fundamental type of diseases.
- Being familiar with type of diseases.
- Learning about type of diseases.

Participants

- Medical professionals
- Medical doctors
- Physicians
- Nurses

Course Details/Schedule

1 day

- X hours

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